

On the Benefits of Point-to-Multipoint Coherent Optics for Multilayer Capacity Planning in Ring Networks with Varying Traffic Profiles

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Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) coherent optics using Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) have recently been proposed as a promising new technology to reduce the cost and complexity of optical transport networks, particularly those in metro aggregation scenarios with Hub-and-Spoke (H&S) traffic patterns. In this paper, we perform a case study on fault tolerant ring networks with more general traffic profiles, to assess the benefits of P2MP optics for alternative network scenarios, like those appearing in metro rings. We propose Mixed Integer Linear Programming formulations for multilayer capacity planning to minimize the total transceiver costs, considering both Point-to-Point (P2P) and P2MP transceivers, as well as a heuristic approach for the more complex P2MP case. Results indicate that P2MP optics can bring several advantages for all tested traffic profiles, ranging from pure uniform flows to mostly H&S. Transceiver cost savings are achieved in various cases, greater at higher network loads and for traffic patterns that are mostly H&S. Results also show that P2MP optics prompt a multilayer redesign of the network with significantly reduced spectrum usage, and a reduced number of IP hops, resulting in Lower Optical-Electronic-Optical and IP processing latency, and lower IP layer equipment costs, for all traffic profiles.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Continued growth in traffic and in capacity requirements caused by the advent of 5G and machine-to-machine (M2M) communication drives the need for innovation to further reduce the cost per transported bit [1]. Improvements have been achieved by combining coherent technology and digital signal processing (DSP), with high-speed analog-to-digital and digital-to-analogue converters. These breakthroughs enabled the transmission of high-order modulation formats over distances ranging from inter datacenter up to ultra-long-haul and improved transmission over point-to-point (P2P) connections. On the other hand, the strong hub & spoke (H&S) pattern of current IP data traffic, can be efficiently tackled with point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) optical transceivers, implemented by exploiting the benefits of digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM). In this technique, a given number of subcarriers (SC)s are digitally generated within the transmitter by employing a single laser. DSCM has been widely investigated to improve transmission performance and it will be discussed in Section 2.

In [2] the authors proposed DSCM to increase network flexibility through the independent allocation of SCs; but only recently, its properties have been exploited with coherent transmission and digital communication to develop a novel P2MP pluggable optics based on DSCM, as presented and demonstrated in [3]-[6]. First commercial products are expected in 2022. DSCM adds new degrees of flexibility and potential cost reductions, particularly in the metro and access segments with H&S traffic flows [3][7][8]. For H&S flows, where several endpoints with low traffic requirements are connected to a smaller number of hub nodes with high aggregated traffic requirements, P2P optical transport technology produces inefficiencies, as transceivers of the same capacity are required at both ends of each optical connection. P2MP technology can overcome this mismatch by subdividing within the transceiver DSP a single carrier wavelength into multiple lower-bandwidth Nyquist subcarriers, which can be independently managed, grouped and routed to different destinations. This allows high speed transceivers at hub nodes to connect directly to multiple lower speed transceivers at different endpoint locations, e.g. by means of a simple

passive optical combiner rather than more complex electrical aggregation stages [3].

Since this technology has only recently been developed, a few studies investigating the possible cost savings of P2MP optical architectures have been performed. Most of them consider H&S traffic flows. In [3], applications of P2MP technology for H&S traffic in passive optical networks and metro aggregation scenarios are presented and potential benefits are discussed. In [7], a CAPEX study indicated significant savings over a 5-year period using P2MP pluggable optics for a reference set of metro network chains and H&S traffic, assuming fixed transceiver costs.

However, to assess the full potential benefits of employing P2MP technology, more studies are needed, not only for H&S traffic, but also for alternative traffic patterns. Following this approach, in [8] we performed a preliminary study on the 5G metro reference scenario described in [9], comprised of a two-tier physical weakly-meshed infrastructure, fixed traffic model and a 2-step multilayer capacity planning algorithm. We compared costs of the capacity planning solution using P2MP pluggable optics versus P2P transceivers and a combination, for different relative transceiver costs. While the results indicate significant CAPEX savings, enabled by P2MP transceivers, this study did not consider limitations due to wavelength blocking for realistic nodal architectures. Furthermore, the capacity planning algorithm was not optimized for P2MP technology.

In this paper, we extend our work from [9] by performing a detailed case study in fault tolerant ring networks. We optimize capacity planning for P2P and P2MP optics considering wavelength blocking constraints incurred by directionless nodes with one add/drop module. Furthermore, we consider different types of traffic profiles, mixing uniform and H&S flows in different proportions and varying the network traffic load. We investigate the multilayer problem, which jointly determines the transceivers allocated to each node, the set of optical connections established between them (along with their associated spectrum assignment), and higher layer packet routing over the optical connections. Fault tolerance to single link failures is assumed for all optical connections, enforced by automatic reconfiguration in the ring optical line system. Note, while the physical routing is straightforward in ring networks, using P2MP transceivers yields new constraints in spectrum assignment, as optical connections are assigned individual subcarriers which can be routed to different destinations. Furthermore, in our study, internal blocking prevents multiple P2MP transceivers at the same node using the same wavelength, even if they use different SCs. This is because the add/drop modules considered are based on a passive mux/demux device, so only one transceiver can be allocated in each port. This will be explained in more detail in Section 3 where we detail the nodal architecture.

We model the problem as a Mixed Integer Linear Program (MILP) considering two variants: one with P2P transceivers and the other with P2MP transceivers, with the overall objective to minimize the total transceiver costs. For larger instances, the exact P2MP MILP cannot provide good suboptimal solutions in reasonable time, so we propose a 2-phase heuristic approach, which combines simplified lower-scale MILP formulations. We investigate the potential benefits of employing P2MP transceivers, not only with respect to total transceiver costs, but also with respect to the number of IP hops (affecting latency and IP layer costs) and spectrum usage. Results indicate that significant transceiver costs savings can be achieved at higher network loads and for higher H&S proportions. Interestingly, P2MP produces denser virtual topologies, with more optical connections, becoming almost a full mesh of optical connections at medium and high loads. Thanks to the subcarrier multiplexing feature, this is done while still providing lower transceiver costs than P2P solutions for higher H&S proportions. Note that such designs would require the number of P2P transceivers to

grow with the square of the number of nodes, while this trend is reduced in P2MP.

Thanks to denser optical connectivity, the average number of IP hops in P2MP networks is in general lower than in P2P-based designs. The lower number of IP hops intrinsically produces networks with less IP traffic processing, and drives towards less IP equipment costs, and lower end-to-end latency, thanks to the reduction of IP processing delays. Additionally, and very importantly, lower average number of IP hops fuels more efficient spectrum usage: the same traffic can be transmitted using less spectrum in the ring. While at lower loads this may not be critical, it becomes crucial at high loads. In fact, P2MP designs were able to carry between 15% to 66% extra capacity compared to P2P solutions in rings using the full C-band for all H&S proportions, except in the case of larger ring (12 nodes) with uniform traffic, where the difference was marginal.

The contributions of this paper are threefold. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study on the benefits of P2MP pluggable optics providing (i) a multilayer capacity planning approach specifically devised to optimize P2MP functionality, (ii) evaluating results for various traffic profiles and (iii) investigating other possible savings beyond transceiver costs, such as IP layer costs and spectrum. The results obtained can provide important insight into the benefits of employing P2MP equipment in future optical networks.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides background on P2MP pluggable coherent optics, followed by a description of the network and node architecture considered in this paper in Section 3. The multilayer capacity planning problem and MILP formulations are presented in Section 4, and numerical results are discussed in Section 5. Conclusions are summarized in Section 6.

2. BACKGROUND

Investment in coherent optical transceiver technology has paid large dividends on several fronts, most notably delivering a steady pace of enhancements in spectral efficiency (SE) and reductions in cost per bit. Operators have been able to keep increasing the capacity deployed over legacy fiber infrastructures and cope with exponential traffic growth without increasing capital expenditures.

Technology roadmaps have delivered these results relying on a) innovation in digital modulation methods for optical transmission; b) enhancements in forward error correction schemes; and c) advancements in photonic integration and Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor (CMOS) application-specific integrated circuits (ASIC)s driving higher symbol rates. This evolution has reached a point where state-of-the-art optical transceivers can deliver SEs very close to the Shannon limit for any given link, and further investment will have diminishing returns [3]. To further complicate matters, symbol rates are now so high that the resulting capacities cannot be utilized efficiently in metro and access networks. This has driven the industry to identify new ways to deliver network cost savings and improvements in SE.

Our study will demonstrate that P2MP optical transmission offers a compelling technology direction, where the overall network flexibility is significantly improved by creating network channels as low as 25G also for coherent technology. The use of DSCM allows mux/demux functions to be realized in the digital domain, together with pre- and post-processing of the individual SCs [10][11].

Fig. 1 depicts an example of experimental spectra of a 400 Gbps signal generated with (a) the traditional single carrier approach at 1×64 GBaud, and (b) its equivalent DSCM using 16×4 GBaud [12]. Both channels have been generated with 16 quadrature amplitude modulation (16QAM) and they occupy the same spectrum. The SCs do not overlap in frequency, and if ideal Nyquist SCs could be generated, there would be no guard-band between them, as reported in [12].

The main difference between a single carrier and a DSCM is that, in the latter case, the transmitter works at a symbol rate, which is scaled by the number S of SCs. The lower bound on the symbol rate in a DSCM-based transceiver is mainly determined by the laser linewidth and by the affordable complexity of the DSP. In fact, a lower symbol rate implies a longer symbol period, and consequently the product (laser linewidth by symbol period) is S times that of a single wavelength [12]. The DSP algorithms within DSCM are the parallelized version of the ones in SC as described in [3]. This presents advantages for what concerns the complexity of the module compensating for the accumulated dispersion as described in [5].

Fig. 1 - Pictorial comparison between a 400G single carrier and its equivalent employing DSCM.

DSCM is not a completely new optical technology. In the past, it has been widely used to: (i) improve physical layer performance in P2P links with respect to fiber nonlinear propagation effects, thanks to the multi-carrier transmission and flexible symbol rate [13][14][15][16]; (ii) optimize the linear compensation [5]; (iii) introduce the flexibility of SCs, allowing the optimization of the channel spectrum to narrow filtering [17]; and (iv) reduce the power consumption by adapting the active SCs dynamically to the instantaneous traffic [18]. Only recently, however, has it been exploited from a networking perspective, to enable a P2MP concept where the SCs can be managed and added/dropped separately in the network. To some extent, DSCM is similar to the sliceable bandwidth transponders proposed in [19].

Such a P2MP feature provides a series of benefits. It is possible to establish optical connections between transceivers at different rates, e.g., a 400G transceiver can establish a $4 \times 25G$ connection using four SCs, with a 100G transceiver. As reported in [3], this removes the need for an

Fig. 2. Ring node architecture.

electrical aggregation stage in some network architectures, which can be replaced now by a simple passive optical combiner/splitter. As a by-product, this has the benefit that a transceiver can be upgraded without affecting the others. Another benefit is that it enables a pay-as-you-grow approach, where an end user can adjust the capacity it needs at a given time [18].

3. NETWORK AND NODE ARCHITECTURE

In this case study, we assume the physical topology is a ring network over which optical connections are established to carry the IP traffic demands. Unregenerated optical reaches of the transceivers are assumed to be enough to enable optical connections between any two nodes in the ring. Note that this assumption is easily satisfied in regional metro networks, with physical lengths of, e.g., 500 km, while coherent transceiver reaches can easily be >1000 km, e.g. by adapting the modulation format. In [7], we reported the applicability to networks of a similar size, with up to 9 intermediate nodes and distances up to 284 km, where the average span length was 16 km. In this analysis, transmission simulations were carried out to verify the margins of the different lightpaths. The considered traffic pattern was H&S. In addition, in [20], we showed the value of P2MP for a network with 106 nodes, ignoring reach aspects.

Fault tolerance to single link failures is included where the primary path is established on the shorter path between the node pair, while the backup path is established on the longer path for each connection. Nodes are assumed to be directionless with one add/drop module, as shown in Fig. 2, and thus subject to internal add/drop blocking. This implies that two optical connections cannot be added (dropped) in the same node in the same wavelength, even if they go out/in through different fibers. Note that the nodes are capable of multicast operation, since lightpaths can be both dropped and bypassed in a node. IP traffic is assumed to be multihop, i.e., can traverse multiple optical connections from source to destination.

The ring network can be built with two types of transceivers: conventional P2P, and DSCM based P2MP transceivers. We consider that (1) all transceivers are bidirectional, with the same rate in both directions, and that (2) the same wavelength is used in transmission and reception connections. While it is possible to build transceivers without such constraints, they are commonplace assumptions in commercial equipment that permit more cost-effective electronics (1) and the use of a single laser source for transmission and coherent reception (2).

The control aspects of the optical line protection scheme, to protect to single link failures, is slightly different in the P2P and P2MP case. In the P2P case, the protection of a wavelength can be implemented sending the optical signal via the shortest path in the ring, shifting to the other path in case of failure. Note that both paths cannot be active at the same time to avoid lasing loops. In the P2MP case, for each wavelength, an optical multicast trail should be configured traversing all the nodes with a transceiver tuned to that wavelength. Then, if a failure affects the trail, a new one should be configured in the surviving topology.

If P2P transceivers are employed, the ones at both end nodes of the optical connection must be of the same rate. Furthermore, since each connection traverses the entire ring, when considering both the primary and backup paths, each connection must use a different allocated spectrum. We will refer to the spectrum allocated to a connection as a *wavelength*, although each wavelength may occupy an arbitrary spectrum depending on the rate of the connection.

If P2MP transceivers are employed, the transceivers at the end nodes of each connection do not need to be of the same rate, and a single wavelength can be used by multiple connections carried on different subcarriers. However, note that two P2MP transceivers at the same node cannot use the same wavelength even if they use different subcarriers, due to internal add/drop blocking at the nodes. We assume

Fig. 3. Example P2P and P2MP transceiver allocation

each P2MP transceiver occupies the spectrum of all the subcarriers, but transmits/receives on any subset of them, which for the sake of simplicity, are not restricted to be contiguous.

In Fig. 3, we can see an example of topology and transceiver allocation with 4 nodes and 6 optical connections along with the IP traffic they carry. Note, a backup path is also established for each connection in the opposite direction in the ring but only the primary paths are shown in the figure for simplicity. Furthermore, in the example we assume both P2P and P2MP solutions have the same IP routing, but in general, this does not need to be the case. Example transceiver allocations, along with subcarrier/wavelength assignment, are shown for P2MP and P2P transceivers. In the P2MP scenario, the connections are established using a 400G transceiver at node 1 and two 100G rate transceivers at each of the remaining nodes. Note, all connections could be established on a single wavelength by employing one 400G P2MP transceiver at each node. However, due to individual transceiver costs, it may be more cost effective to use two 100G transceivers rather than one 400G at a node, if less than nine subcarriers are transmitted/received. In the P2P scenario, ten 100G and two 25G transceivers are needed to carry the IP traffic on six wavelengths (which may occupy arbitrary amounts of spectrum).

4. MULTILAYER CAPACITY PLANNING AND TRANSCEIVER ALLOCATION IN RING NETWORKS

This section formally describes the problem of multilayer capacity planning and transceiver allocation in ring networks and provides a set of MILP formulations to find the optimum allocation of P2P and P2MP transceivers, the optical connections between them, and the routing of the packet traffic over those connections. The optimization target is the total cost minimization coming from the transceivers installed, having

the minimization of the average number of IP hops as a secondary objective. A 2-phase heuristic combining simplified MILP formulations is also proposed for the P2MP case.

A. Problem definition

The problem definition and the notation is summarized in Table 1. Let $G(N,F)$ be a ring network with a set of nodes N and a set of unidirectional fibers F , so two neighbor nodes are connected by two fibers, one in each direction. We use $\#N$ to denote the number of nodes, and n to denote a node in N . We assume that nodes are numbered with an index, $i=0,\dots,\#N-1$, and that a node n_i is connected to nodes n_{i+1} and n_{i-1} in the topology.

We use R to denote the set of selectable transceiver rates in Gbps. We consider valid rates to be $R=\{25, 100, 400\}$. We assume that P2MP transceivers are based on 25 Gbps subcarriers, and denote as $sc(r)$ the number of 25G subcarriers or capacity modules, associated to a rate r (i.e. $r/25$). Then, the full P2MP signal is composed of 16 subcarriers, and 25G transceivers can process one out of the 16 subcarriers, 100G transceivers four, and 400G transceivers all of them. In 100G transceivers, for the sake of simplicity, the four subcarriers do not have the constraint of being spectrum contiguous.

We denote as c_r the cost of a P2P transceiver at rate r . Then, we assume that the cost of P2MP at rate r , is $(1+\alpha)c_r$, i.e. α represents the proportional extra cost of P2MP transceivers (assuming $\alpha \geq 0$) respect to P2P transceivers. Still, it is worth to be mentioned that if used in P2P operation, P2MP transceivers present the same estimated cost of P2P ones. We assume in this formulation that both P2P and P2MP transceivers occupy one wavelength, out of the set W of usable ones. As previously mentioned, we assume that transceivers are bidirectional, with the same rate in both directions, and the same wavelength is used in transmission and reception connections.

We consider that P2P and P2MP are not compatible technologies, and a wavelength w can be allocated for i) two P2P transceivers at the same rate with one bidirectional optical connection between them, or else ii) two or more P2MP transceivers, potentially of different rates (thanks to the subcarrier aggregation capability), and with several bidirectional optical connections among them, each occupying a number of subcarriers among the 16 available.

Note, as mentioned in the previous section, that we are *not* assuming here that all the wavelengths occupy the same bandwidth. While this can reasonably be the case for P2P and P2MP transceivers at its maximum rate (400G), it is not the same for lower rate P2P transceivers, which could enjoy occupying a lower amount of spectrum than their P2MP counterparts. To capture this, we denote $bw(r)$ to the bandwidth in GHz occupied by a wavelength with two P2P transceivers at rate r , and use $bw(R_{max})$ to denote the bandwidth for the maximum rate (400 Gbps in our tests), which is considered to be the same as the bandwidth of P2MP transceivers at *any* rate. Finally, the total spectrum available in the network in GHz, or else, the tuning range of the transceivers, is denoted as BW , which equals 4.6 THz in our tests, representing the full C-band.

The higher layer (e.g, IP/MPLS) packet traffic demand to carry is given by a set D of demands. Given a demand $d \in D$, $a(d)$ denotes its origin node, $b(d)$ its destination node, and $h(d)$ the traffic to carry, measured in Gbps. Multilayer network operation is considered, where the traffic between two nodes, can be carried:

- In multi-hop operation: The traffic from e.g, n_1 to n_5 , can go through an optical connection (between P2P or P2MP transceivers) from n_1 to n_2 , be electronically switched to another transceiver in node n_2 , and then transmitted via a second optical connection from n_2 to n_5 (again, between P2P or P2MP transceivers).
- In bifurcated form: All the traffic between two nodes does not have to follow the same sequence of optical connections, and thus do not have to traverse the same sequence of transceivers. The IP/MPLS layer is assumed to be able to implement such a routing profile, e.g, using standardized options like MPLS-TE tunnels.

We denote as C the set of all possible unidirectional (n,n') pairs that can be created in the ring (i.e., $\#N(\#N-1)$ of them), and we denote as C' the set of all bidirectional connections (i.e. $\#N(\#N-1)/2$ of them, since connections (n,n') and (n',n) would be the same). Given a node n , $C^+(n)$ and $C^-(n)$ are the unidirectional connections outgoing and incoming from n , respectively. Similarly, $C(n)$ are the bidirectional connections which have n as an end node. Given a unidirectional connection c , we denote as $c'(c)$ the associated bidirectional connection between its end nodes.

The set C will be used in the representation of the routing of the packet traffic, and the set C' will be used to represent the optical connections between two transceivers on the same wavelength (P2P transceivers, or two P2MP transceivers out of the ones using the same wavelength, exchanging data in at least one subcarrier).

The network is designed to be fault tolerant to single duct cuts, that is, the failure of one or two of the fibers connecting two node neighbor nodes. This is accomplished as follows:

- All the optical connections are optically routed via the shortest physical path between the end nodes. In P2MP connections, where three or more nodes are engaged, two of them are selected that have a path in the ring that traverses all the rest of the end nodes. Such a path is considered the optical multicast trail connecting the

nodes, and the wavelength blockers in Fig. 2 would be configured accordingly.

- If a fiber link (with one fiber in each direction) is cut in one or both directions, the multicast trails or the P2P connections are remade in the surviving topology, using the same wavelength.

This fault tolerance strategy means that when two (or more, in the P2MP case) transceivers are connected in each wavelength, such a wavelength should be reserved, and not reused for other purpose in all the ring, since any fiber link could be traversed by the connection in at least one of the failure states considered.

Table 1. Problem notation summary

Parameter/variable	Definition
$N = \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_{\#N}\}$	Set of nodes
$F = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_{\#F}\}$	Set of unidirectional fibers
$R = \{25, 100, 400\}$	Set of selectable transceiver rates in Gbps
R_{max}	Maximum rate (400 Gbps in our tests)
$sc(r)$	Number of 25G subcarriers or capacity modules associated to a rate r
c_r	Cost of a P2P transceiver at rate r
α	Proportional extra cost of P2MP transceivers respect to P2P transceivers
$W = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{\#W}\}$	Set of wavelengths
$bw(r)$	Bandwidth in GHz occupied by a wavelength with two P2P transceivers at rate r
BW	Total spectrum available in the network in GHz / tuning range of the transceivers
$D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{\#D}\}$	Set of IP packet demands
$a(d)$	Origin node of demand d
$b(d)$	Destination node of demand d
$h(d)$	Amount of offered traffic of demand d in Gbps
$C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{\#C}\}$	Set of all possible unidirectional (n,n') pairs (connections) that can be created in the ring
$C' = \{c'_1, c'_2, \dots, c'_{\#C'}\}$	Set of all bidirectional connections
$C^+(n)$	Number of unidirectional connections outgoing from n
$C^-(n)$	Number of unidirectional connections incoming from n
$C(n)$	Number of bidirectional connections which have n as an end node
$c'(c)$	Associated bidirectional connection between the ends nodes of the unidirectional connection c .

B. Mixed P2P/P2MP MILP Formulation

This subsection describes the MILP formulation for the general problem that finds the combination of P2P and P2MP transceivers (permitting hybrid networks mixing both P2P and P2MP technologies using non-overlapping wavelengths), that optimizes the total network cost. IP hops are also minimized, as a secondary objective.

The decision variables of the problem are:

- x_{dc} , for all $d \in D, c \in C$, represents the amount of traffic (in Gbps) for packet demand d , in any of the optical connections between the end nodes of c ;

- u_{cw} , for all $c \in \mathcal{C}$, $w \in \mathcal{W}$, represents the integer number of subcarriers (or 25G modules of capacity) of the optical connection between the end nodes of c , in wavelength w , or 0 if no optical connection exists;
- $p2mp_w$ for all $w \in \mathcal{W}$, is 1 if wavelength w is used for connecting two or more P2MP transceivers at wavelength w , 0 otherwise;
- $p2p_{rwn}$, for all $r \in \mathcal{R}$, $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $n \in \mathcal{N}$, is 1 if a P2P transceiver at rate r , is allocated at node n , and tuned at wavelength w , 0 otherwise;
- $p2mp_{rwn}$, for all $r \in \mathcal{R}$, $w \in \mathcal{W}$, $n \in \mathcal{N}$, is 1 if a P2MP transceiver at rate r , is allocated at node n , and tuned at wavelength w , 0 otherwise.

The problem constraints are:

- *Packet traffic flow conservation constraints.* Ensure that, for all the packet traffic demands, all the traffic must be carried, allowing bifurcated traffic routing.

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}^+(n)} x_{dc} - \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}^-(n)} x_{dc} &= h(d), \text{ if } n = a(d) \\ \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}^+(n)} x_{dc} - \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}^-(n)} x_{dc} &= -h(d), \text{ if } n = b(d) \\ \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}^+(n)} x_{dc} - \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}^-(n)} x_{dc} &= 0, \text{ otherwise} \end{aligned} \quad (1a)$$

$$\forall d \in \mathcal{D}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}$$

- *Optical capacity constraints.* Force the capacity planned, in number of subcarriers (or 25 Gbps capacity modules), between every two nodes, to be enough to carry the packet traffic between them.

$$\sum_d x_{dc} \leq 25 \sum_w u_{c'(c)w}, \forall c \in \mathcal{C} \quad (1b)$$

- *Transceiver rate and wavelength allocation constraint.* Ensures that P2P and/or P2MP transceivers are allocated with the required rate and wavelength, to carry the optical connections.

$$\sum_r sc(r)(p2p_{rwn} + p2mp_{rwn}) \geq \sum_{c' \in \mathcal{C}'(n)} u_{c'w}, \quad (1c)$$

$$\forall c \in \mathcal{C}$$

- *Wavelength capacity constraint.* Establishes that each wavelength can allocate at most 16 subcarriers

$$\sum_{c'} u_{c'w} \leq 16, \forall w \in \mathcal{W} \quad (1d)$$

- *P2MP vs P2P incompatibility constraints.* Allows a wavelength to be used for P2P transceivers or for P2MP transceivers, but not both

$$p2mp_{rwn} \leq p2p_{rwn}, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}, w \in \mathcal{W}, n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (1e)$$

$$p2p_{rwn} \leq (1 - p2mp_w), \forall r \in \mathcal{R}, w \in \mathcal{W}, n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (1f)$$

- *Wavelength clashing constraint.* Ensures that most one transceiver can exist in each node, tuned to a particular wavelength.

$$\sum_r p2p_{rwn} + p2mp_{rwn} \leq 1, \forall w \in \mathcal{W}, n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (1g)$$

- *Point-to-point constraint.* Limits that in P2P wavelengths, there cannot be more than two transceivers (naturally, in different nodes).

$$\sum_{r,n} p2p_{rwn} \leq 2, \forall w \in \mathcal{W} \quad (1h)$$

- *Total spectrum constraint.* Ensures that spectrum occupied does not exceed the available amount. The first constraint sums the spectrum occupied by P2P transceivers (two per wavelength), and the second sums the spectrum of the P2MP transceivers.

$$\sum_{r,w,n} \left(\frac{bw(r)}{2} \right) p2p_{rwn} + bw(R_{max}) \sum_w p2mp_w \leq BW \quad (1i)$$

The objective function (1j) used in this paper minimizes the network cost coming from the transceivers installed, while the average IP hops is minimized as a secondary objective. The latter is achieved by multiplying the sum of the IP routing decision variables by a sufficiently small factor ϵ . In our tests, ϵ was set so that the cost of adding one extra 25G transceiver was the same as the cost of routing 1 Tbps of traffic, which effectively means that IP hop minimization was a secondary objective respect to transceiver cost minimization.

$$\text{Min} \sum_{r,w,n} c_r p2p_{rwn} + (1 + \alpha) c_r p2mp_{rwn} + \epsilon \sum_{d,c} x_{dc} \quad (1j)$$

C. Pure P2P and Pure P2MP MILP formulations

The general formulation described in the previous section can be simplified to design networks that can only use P2P transceivers, or networks with only P2MP transceivers.

Pure P2P network designs

For P2P network designs, multiple simplifications can be made which yield a compact MILP. The key complexity reduction comes from the possibility of dropping all the P2MP variables, as well as the wavelength w subindex in the variables, since all the P2P connections must involve two transceivers and occupy one wavelength.

The updated decision variables are:

- x_{dc} for all $d \in \mathcal{D}$, $c \in \mathcal{C}$, representing the amount of traffic (in Gbps) for packet demand d , in any of the optical connections between the end nodes of c ;
- $p2p_m$ for all $r \in \mathcal{R}$, $n \in \mathcal{N}$, is 1 if a P2P transceiver at rate r , is allocated at node n , 0 otherwise.

The problem constraints are:

- Flow conservation constraints. Same as (1a);
- *Optical capacity constraints.* Ensure the IP traffic should be transported in optical connections of sufficient capacity.

$$\sum_r r \cdot p2p_{rc(c)} \geq \sum_d x_{dc}, \forall c \in \mathcal{C} \quad (2a)$$

- *Total spectrum constraints.* Ensure the spectrum occupation does not exceed the limits

$$\sum_{r,c'} \left(\frac{bw(r)}{2} \right) p2p_{rc'} \leq BW \quad (2b)$$

Pure P2MP network designs

The simplification in this case comes from simply discarding the decision variables and constraints of the general problem that have to do with P2P transceivers:

- The decision variables removed are: $p2p_{rwn}$ and $p2mp_w$;
- Flow conservation constraints (1a), optical capacity constraints (1b) and wavelength capacity constraints (1d) remain unchanged;
- Constraint (1e) is kept to account for the total number of wavelengths used, while incompatibility constraint (1f) is removed;
- The P2P constraint (1h) is removed;
- Transceiver rate constraints (1c), wavelength clashing (1g) constraints and total spectrum constraints (1i) are modified by removing the P2P contribution:

$$\sum_r sc(r) p2mp_{rwn} \geq \sum_{c' \in C'(n)} u_{c'w}, \forall c \in C \quad (3a)$$

$$\sum_r p2mp_{rwn} \leq 1, \forall w \in W, n \in N \quad (3b)$$

$$bw(R_{max}) \sum_w p2mp_w \leq BW \quad (3c)$$

- The objective function removes the P2P contribution and, thus, can drop parameter α since only P2MP transceivers are considered.

D. Pure P2MP heuristic approach

In our tests, the pure P2MP simplified formulation (3) permitted us to solve to optimality, or with optimality gaps below 5%, small size rings (e.g. 6 nodes), in a time below ten minutes. However, for larger rings the MILP algorithm could not find reasonably good solutions for many instances, even after several hours.

To complete the required tests for our analysis, a heuristic approach was designed. The heuristic is based on a two-phase process:

- *Phase 1. Single IP hop P2MP design.* In this phase, a solution is created where all the IP traffic between each pair of nodes, is carried in direct subcarriers between the end nodes;
- *Phase 2. Transceiver cost reduction.* In this phase, the IP routing and optical connections coming from the previous phase are reoptimized to target transceiver cost minimization, with the restrictions that 1) new transceivers cannot be added, and 2) existing ones must keep their wavelength, but can optionally reduce their rate or be eliminated.

These phases are implemented by the lower-scale MILPs, described in the next subsection. These MILPs have shown to be runnable for the network scales of interest, returning good solutions, with running times in the order of few minutes, as will be reported in Section 5.

Phase 1: Single IP hop P2MP heuristic

In this phase, the heuristic starts with the IP traffic matrix to be carried. Then, an iterative process is initiated, which allocates in each iteration the transceivers to be used in a single wavelength, carrying as much

pending traffic as possible, minimizing the transceiver cost as a second objective. The process ends when no more pending traffic exists. Inside each iteration, a small-scale MILP is solved, which has shown to produce optimal solutions in less than one second in most of our tests, and always below a few seconds. The decision variables of this MILP are:

- $u_{c'}$, for all $c' \in C'$, represents the integer number of subcarriers (or 25G modules of capacity) of the optical connection between the end nodes of c' , in the current wavelength, or 0 if no optical connection exists;
- $p2p_m$, for all $r \in R$, $n \in N$, is 1 if a P2P transceiver at rate r , is allocated at node n , at the current iteration wavelength, 0 otherwise.

The problem constraints are:

- *Pending traffic limit constraint.* For each node pair (n, n') , the decision variables $u_{c'}$, cannot exceed the number of pending 25G modules needed to carry the traffic not yet carried between the connection end nodes, denoted as $tm(c')$. Note that, if (n, n') are the connection end nodes, this corresponds to the maximum between the pending traffic from n to n' , and from n' to n .

$$u_{c'} \leq \text{ceil} \left(\frac{tm(c')}{25} \right), \forall c' \in C' \quad (4a)$$

- *Transceiver rate constraint.* Ensures that P2MP transceivers are allocated with the required rate, to carry the needed direct IP traffic.

$$\sum_r sc(r) p2p_{rn} \geq \sum_{c' \in C'(n)} u_{c'}, \forall c \in C \quad (4b)$$

- *Wavelength capacity constraint.* This constraints states that each wavelength can allocate at most 16 subcarriers.

$$\sum_{c'} u_{c'w} \leq 16, \forall w \in W \quad (4c)$$

- *Wavelength clashing constraint.* Ensures that at most one transceiver can exist in each node.

$$\sum_r p2mp_{rn} \leq 1, \forall n \in N \quad (4d)$$

The objective function ensures that as many subcarriers as possible are carried (primary target), with the minimum transceiver cost (secondary target):

$$\text{Max } M \sum_{c'} u_{c'} - \sum_{rn} c_r p2mp_{rn} \quad (4e)$$

Where M is a constant large enough to make the maximization of the carried traffic the primary optimization target. Note that this is needed, otherwise the minimum cost solution would be not carrying IP traffic at all. In our case, M was set as a hundred times the cost of the most expensive transceiver.

Phase 2: Transceiver cost reduction

The transceiver reduction phase is implemented by running a simplified version of formulation (3), where some of the decision variables are removed, by fixing their values to zero:

- $p2p_{rwn}$ is set to zero when the solution coming from the previous phase has no transceiver at node n on wavelength w with rate r or larger;
- u_{cw} is set to zero if no transceiver on wavelength w , with any rate, was allocated in the previous phase, to the end nodes of connection c .

E. Complexity Analysis

Table 2 compares the complexity of the described MILP formulations in terms of the number of variables and constraints. We assume traffic flows between all pairs of nodes, so $D=N(N-1)$. Furthermore, assuming a fully connected IP topology, the number of optical connections is $C=N(N-1)$. Under these assumptions, the dominant terms in the number of variables for the Mixed P2P/P2MP and Pure P2MP formulations are N^4+N^2W , and the number of constraints N^4+2RWN and N^4+RWN , respectively. The dominant term in the Pure P2P MILP formulation is N^4 for both variables and constraints. Regarding the heuristic, Phase 1 is of lower complexity with dominant term N^2 for both variables and constraints. Phase 2 of the P2P heuristic, although having the same general number of variables and constraints as the Pure P2MP formulation, is typically reduced in practical terms as many variables are set to 0. This complexity reduction permitted us to run this phase for all the instances in our tests, obtaining good solutions with a time limitation of 5 minutes, yielding the results described in Section 5.

Table 2. Number of variables and constraints in the MILP formulations

Problem	Variables	Constraints
Mixed P2P/P2MP	DC+CW+W+2RWN	DN+2C+2RWN+WN+2W+1
Pure P2P	DC+RN	DN+C+1
Pure P2MP	DC+CW+RWN	DN+2C+WN+RWN+1
P2MP Ph. 1	C+RN	2C+W+N
P2MP Ph. 2	DC+CW +RWN*	DN+2C+WN+RWN+1

*Same complexity as Pure P2P but significantly lower practical size, as many variables are set to 0

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS

A. SIMULATION SETUP

In this paper, we are interested in evaluating the potentials of P2MP technologies, for replacing traditional P2P transceivers in fault tolerant optical ring networks, as the ones described in Section 3. Such networks appear in different application scopes such as:

- Rings inside the so-called metro access, consisting of metro nodes connecting to access network nodes, e.g., the mobile fronthaul and backhaul network;
- Rings at the metro-core, consisting of higher capacity nodes in the regional metro network, aggregating traffic from metro access nodes, and connecting the metro to the network core nodes.

Results are elaborated for optical rings with the number of nodes $\#N=\{6, 9, 12\}$, which cover the range of typical ring sizes in our target scopes [9][21].

While advantages of P2MP for H&S traffic flows are intuitive, we would like to investigate the benefits of this technology for alternative IP packet traffic patterns. In this paper, we consider traffic profiles (i) at different

network loads, and (ii) with different distributions by mixing in different proportions: uniform traffic flows (where the outgoing demands of each node are equally split among the rest of the nodes) and H&S traffic flows (where nodes send traffic to a reduced number of hub nodes in the ring). To model such traffic profiles, we make the traffic dependent on two parameters:

- ρ : Network load, measured as the average traffic in Gbps generated by each node. Note that this means that the total traffic in the ring is equal to $\rho\#N$.
- HS (%): Fraction $[0,1]$ of packet traffic that is of hub-spoke nature. The remaining traffic is uniform.

The traffic matrix generated $TM(i,j)$, containing the traffic from node i to node j is computed as follows:

- 1) A non-normalized uniform traffic matrix is created (TM_u), where all the nodes send one unit of traffic to the rest of the nodes.
- 2) A non-normalized hub-spoke traffic matrix is created (TM_{hs}) where the network has two hub nodes. These hub nodes send 0.1 units of traffic to each other, and 1 unit of traffic to the spoke nodes, and spoke nodes send 1 unit of traffic to each of the hub nodes, and no traffic to other spoke nodes.
- 3) Previous non-normalized traffic matrices are now normalized, multiplying each of them by the appropriate value, so the sum of all the elements in the uniform traffic matrix normalized becomes $\rho(\#N)(1-HS)$, and the sum of all the elements in the hub-spoke traffic matrix normalized becomes $\rho(\#N)HS$.
- 4) The two matrices produced in the previous step are aggregated into one. Then, each traffic coordinate is multiplied by a random number uniformly chosen between 0.9 and 1.1, to produce random traffic variations.
- 5) The random traffic matrix produced is normalized again, so the sum of its elements becomes $\rho(\#N)$.

The fraction of H&S traffic for each case was varied in $HS=\{0\%, 30\%, 60\%, 90\%\}$. Note that the proportions of the H&S traffic in our tests refers to the higher layer IP traffic. Since we assume multihop routing, this does not mean that the optical layer connections are necessarily H&S in the exact same proportions as the IP traffic, although they will generally follow the trend of the IP traffic. The traffic load ρ was varied among values $\{100, 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000\}$ (Gbps), and from 1000 Gbps onwards in increments of 500 Gbps, up until the allocated spectrum reached 4.6 THz, i.e. until the C-band was saturated. To calculate the spectrum required for each connection, we assume an optical line system in the ring able to filter at a 12.5 GHz granularity. Then, optical connections will occupy an integer number of such slots. Transceiver rates considered are $R=\{25G, 100G, 400G\}$, with 25G subcarriers for the P2MP case. Individual transceiver costs for P2P and P2MP equipment are those shown in Table 3 following the cost model from [21]. P2MP transceivers are assumed to have proportional cost, incremented by a factor $\alpha \geq 0$. Note that according to the cost model, 25G transceivers have 70% of the cost of 100G transceivers, while providing 25% of the rate, and thus becoming a solution with potentially little application interest. This is consistent with the fact that, to the best of the author's knowledge, no commercial 25G coherent option exists at the moment of writing this paper. Still, we preferred to include it in this paper to cover this potential alternative, and for giving P2P an

Fig. 4. Transceiver costs of the P2P and P2MP ($\alpha=0$) solutions for (a) HS=0%, (b) HS=30%, (c) HS=60%, and (d) HS=90%,

opportunity to match the P2MP capability to offer connections at a 25G granularity, thanks to its subcarrier multiplexing scheme.

Table 3. Transceiver costs

Rate	Normalized cost	
	P2P	P2MP
25G	3.5	$(1+\alpha)\cdot 3.5$
100G	5	$(1+\alpha)\cdot 5$
400G	12	$(1+\alpha)\cdot 12$

For P2MP transceivers, we base on the spectrum performances published e.g. in [2], which specifies an occupation of 64 GHz for the P2MP 400G signal, and implies an effective occupation of 75 GHz of spectrum in the network (6 slots of 12.5 GHz). We assume that P2MP of

lower rates also occupy the full 75 GHz. Contrarily, for the P2P case, we assume that transceivers transmit signals with bandwidth proportional to their rate (assuming zero guard bands), with that of 400G being equal to the P2MP case giving: 4 GHz for 25G, 16 GHz for 100G, and 64 GHz for 400G. However, given the requirement of adapting to the 12.5 GHz grid, this translates into occupations of 12.5 GHz (25G), 25GHz (100G) and 75 GHz (400G). Note, the spectrum waste in P2P 25G is significant (4 GHz translates to 12.5 GHz occupation). However, this reflects the fact that as line rates grow, subcarriers provide a finer granularity to fraction the bandwidth, beyond what commercial optical line systems can currently provide. Finally, it is relevant to note that in the P2MP case, a wavelength would not need to occupy 75 GHz in all the cases, but only in those cases where at least one of the transceivers involved is of 400G. Still, we included this simplification in our experiments, which makes P2MP spectrum management operationally simpler than in the P2P case.

B. RESULTS

Herein we compare the results of capacity planning solutions using P2P vs. P2MP transceivers for different network sizes and varying traffic patterns as described in the previous subsection. All MILP formulations were executed on an Intel Core i7-7500U laptop, with 32 GB of RAM, using CPLEX solver (v 12.1). The maximum running time was set to 5 minutes for each individual MILP, returning the best solution found after that time. Five randomized instances were run for each parameter setting. Average results are presented in this section, while the distribution of the results among the samples is not shown to simplify the plots. However, the variability observed between samples with the same parameter settings was relatively small and did not contradict the main trends reported.

The P2P solutions are those obtained by solving the pure P2P MILP formulation described in Section 4B. For $\#N=6$, the solver could find the optimal solutions in less than 5 minutes, while for 9 and 12 nodes the solutions presented are those returned after the 5 minutes time limit, with optimality gaps reported by the solver below 5% in most of the cases as shown in Table 4. Since optimality gaps are mostly dependent on load, differing very little between other parameter settings, the gaps are shown averaged for each load factor. While high optimality gaps occur for low loads (≤ 400 Gbps) in terms of percentage, these solutions correspond to low absolute costs as will be shown in Figure 4.

For P2MP, the exact MILP was too complex to find good suboptimal solutions for 9 and 12 nodes even for longer running times. Consequently, for the P2MP scenario, the results presented are those obtained by the heuristic approach described in Section 4C where the runtime of the MILP in Phase 2 of the heuristic was set to 5 minutes with average optimality gaps per load those presented in Table 4. Phase 1 of the heuristic ran under 1 minute in all cases. To assess the efficiency of this heuristic approach, both the exact P2MP formulation from 4B and heuristic were run for $\#N=6$, where the heuristic gave results on average 5% over that obtained by the exact formulation.

Table 4. Average MILP Optimality Gaps

Load [Gbps]	N=9		N=12	
	P2P MILP	P2MP Heuristic Ph. 2 MILP	P2P MILP	P2MP Heuristic Ph. 2 MILP
100	20.0%	5.3%	37.3%	26.8%
200	11.8%	5.0%	38.5%	23.5%
400	8.5%	9.3%	16.5%	27.8%
600	3.8%	12.3%	7.0%	24.0%
800	3.0%	11.3%	6.0%	21.8%
1000	0.3%	12.5%	1.8%	14.8%
1500	1.8%	10.0%	5.5%	17.0%
2000	1.3%	9.8%	2.5%	15.8%
2500	0.5%	7.8%	0.3%	13.0%
3000	0.3%	6.0%	0.3%	12.0%
3500	1.0%	5.5%	1.0%	10.5%
4000	1.0%	6.0%	-	-

Transceiver costs

In Fig. 4, we compare the transceiver costs of the solutions obtained with P2P and P2MP transceivers for all three networks for different H&S proportions. Note, results are shown for $\alpha=0$, where the cost of P2P and P2MP transceivers are assumed to be equal. The actual savings will depend on the difference in cost of P2MP equipment over P2P equipment, once they become commercial. Results are shown for each network up to the load values for which *both* P2P and P2MP could find solutions without saturating the spectrum. Recall, P2MP could find

solutions for higher loads than P2P for all networks, but this will be discussed in the next subsection on spectrum usage.

We can observe from Fig. 4 that P2MP produces in most of the cases a reduction in transceiver costs. This is more significant at higher loads (up to the load that P2P can reach), and particularly for higher proportions of H&S traffic. For $\#N=6$ nodes, the transceiver costs of the P2P and P2MP solutions are within 5% of each other for loads between 400 -1500 Gbps and all HS fractions. As the load is increased beyond these values, P2MP offers increasing cost savings, with maximal values ranging from 49% cost savings for HS=0% at maximal load $\rho=5000$ Gbps to 57% for HS=90% at maximal load $\rho=4500$ Gbps.

Although P2MP also brings high relative savings for loads below 400 Gbps (up to 36%), the absolute savings are not very significant. For larger networks, the maximal cost savings achieved reached 35% and 23% for 9 and 12 nodes, respectively, for HS=90%. However, note that these maximal savings correspond to lower load values than for $\#N=6$, as the spectrum was saturated by P2P at per-node loads of 3000 Gbps (9 nodes) and 2500Gbps (12 nodes). If equal load values are considered, savings are similar for all network sizes for high HS proportions. For larger networks, high relative savings were also achieved for loads below 400 Gbps (even up to 57%) but, as previously mentioned, the absolute savings at lower loads are more marginal.

For lower HS proportions (more uniform traffic) and larger networks, in several cases P2P gives lower cost solutions than P2MP, being in the order of 5% for 9 nodes and 10% for 12 nodes. Since P2MP transceivers can perform the same functions as P2P transceivers, the optimal cost P2MP solutions (assuming $\alpha=0$) should always be at least as good as the P2P solutions. However, since we are using a heuristic approach for P2MP which gives suboptimal solutions, this is not always the case. Furthermore, due to the more significant optimality gaps for larger networks, it is difficult to assess the actual savings for these cases. Other work has shown P2MP savings to be independent of the traffic pattern [20], which suggests more work in this area may be required. However, although the suboptimal solutions found by our heuristic approach do not bring transceiver cost savings for low HS fractions in larger networks, they still offer other advantages, such as better spectrum usage and reduced latency, which will be discussed in the next subsections.

Spectrum usage and network capacity

In this subsection, we compare the spectrum used by the solutions obtained with P2P and P2MP equipment. Recall that for the P2MP solutions, each wavelength is assumed to occupy 75 GHz of spectrum, whatever the number of subcarriers used, while for P2P, 25G occupies 12.5 GHz, 100G 25 GHz, and 400G 75 GHz.

To gain insight into dependency of spectrum usage on HS proportion, Fig. 5 shows the ratio of the spectrum occupied in the P2P solutions over that used in the P2MP solutions, for all HS fractions and all 3 network sizes. Here, ratios over 1 indicate that the P2MP solutions occupy less spectrum. We can see that P2MP solutions outperform P2P for all HS proportions at almost all loads. While for lower loads the relative savings are somewhat higher for lower HS fractions, as the load increases beyond 2000 Gbps where absolute differences are more significant, we can see that P2MP brings higher savings for higher HS fractions.

In Fig. 6, we plot the spectrum used in the P2P and P2MP solutions for HS=30% traffic and all 3 network sizes. Results are shown for all loads for which the allocated spectrum is below 4.6THz for each transceiver type, i.e., before saturation of the C-band. The savings obtained by employing P2MP transceivers ranges from 50 to 400 GHz for lower loads, to a maximal of 1.58 THz, 500 GHz and 480 GHz for the maximal network loads P2P can accommodate for 6, 9, and 12 nodes, respectively.

Fig. 5. Ratio of spectrum usage in the P2P to P2MP solutions for for (a) $\#N=6$, (b) $\#N=9$, (c) $\#N=12$ nodes.

Fig. 6. Spectrum usage (Thz) of the P2P to P2MP solutions for $H=30\%$ for (a) $\#N=6$, (b) $\#N=9$, (c) $\#N=12$ nodes.

In summary, the results clearly state an advantage in terms of spectrum occupation of designs employing P2MP transceivers. At first glance, this observation seems inconsistent with the fact that P2MP transceivers occupy in our tests the full 75 GHz slots irrespective of the number of subcarriers used, while for P2P more flexibility is assumed. What fuels this P2MP reduced spectrum usage, then? The answer to this question is the denser IP topology that P2MP permits, with more direct optical connections between nodes, enabling IP traffic to be carried traversing a lower number of optical connections across the ring. This will be witnessed by the average IP hop results shown in the next section and discussed in the summary subsection.

Table 5 collects information on the maximum amount of traffic the network can carry in our tests for different ring sizes and hub-spoke traffic factors. Note that results are shown, not in average load per node (ρ), but as the total traffic ($\rho\#N$). Results expose the advantages of P2MP designs with respect to ring capacity, a natural consequence of the P2MP reduced spectrum occupation. P2MP provides large relative extra capacity in many cases, particularly for higher HS factors and in smaller networks. Even in the worst case of $N=12$ and uniform traffic, where both designs could carry 42 Tbps, P2MP required around 0.2 THz less spectrum, which could be used for future connections. Finally, we would like to point out that as fiber scarcity is a real issue, P2MP

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 7. The average number of IP hops in the P2P to P2MP solutions for (a) $\#N=6$, (b) $\#N=9$, (c) $\#N=12$ nodes

more efficient utilization of the spectrum, may translate into additional cost savings.

Table 5. Ring capacity P2MP / P2P (Tbps)

	$\#N=6$	$\#N=9$	$\#N=12$
HS 0%	45/30 (+50%)	45/36 (+25%)	42/42 (+0%)
HS 30%	45/30 (+50%)	45/36 (+25%)	42/36 (+16%)
HS 60%	45/30 (+50%)	45/31.5 (+42%)	42/36 (+16%)
HS 90%	45/27 (+66%)	45/27 (+66%)	42/30 (+40%)

IP Hops: latency and IP layer costs

Fig. 7 (a), (b), and (c), plot the average number of IP hops in the P2P and P2MP solutions for 6, 9 and 12 nodes, respectively, for loads up to spectrum saturation. We can see that P2MP gives solutions with significantly fewer IP hops in almost all cases for all three networks. Moreover, P2MP provides nearly single hop solutions for almost all loads (especially above 1000 Gbps) and all HS proportions. P2P, on the other hand, varies significantly with load and HS proportion. For lower loads, P2P solutions traverse less IP hops for higher fractions of HS traffic, while for higher loads, they give fewer IP hops for more uniform traffic. Note that the reduction in IP hops is more significant for larger

networks for more uniform traffic, supporting the use of P2MP even for cases where transceiver costs are not reduced. More specifically, for loads below 1000 Gbps, P2P yields on average 47% more IP hops than the P2MP solutions for uniform traffic and 15% more IP hops for HS=90%, over all 3 networks. For loads above 1000 Gbps, P2P gives solutions with 20% more IP hops for uniform traffic, and 36% more for HS=90%. For lower loads, less optical connections are established, and they can be arranged more favorably for HS traffic. For higher loads, more higher capacity connections are established throughout the network giving less IP hops for uniform traffic. The fact that all P2P curves exhibit a decrease at intermediate loads for all HS proportions is presumably due to cases where the granularity of the transceiver rates coincides better with the network load and P2P solutions are similar to those obtained by P2MP, which can be observed also in spectrum and cost results. This will be discussed further in the next subsection.

Summary and discussion

In summary, results indicate that employing P2MP transceivers can offer important benefits for all types of traffic flows. More specifically, P2MP technology can bring significant transceiver costs savings at higher loads for higher HS fractions. Although transceiver costs are not reduced at higher loads and lower HS proportions for larger networks (presumably due to the suboptimality of the P2MP solutions in the MILP

framework) and reductions are marginal in general at lower loads for all HS proportions, P2MP optics can provide other advantages. Namely, P2MP solutions offer a more efficient spectrum usage and fewer IP hops for almost all loads and traffic distributions.

Relative savings of P2MP over P2P are larger for more uniform traffic at low loads, particularly in terms of spectrum and IP hops, while offering more significant advantages for higher HS proportions at higher loads. This makes sense, since for low loads, a uniform distribution creates several lower rate flows (<100 Gbps) which could be aggregated using P2MP equipment. For higher loads, individual flows of uniform traffic are of higher rates and in many cases can be established using higher rate P2P transceivers.

In general, the relative savings with respect to transceiver costs, spectrum and IP hops for all traffic distributions are larger at low loads, decrease for intermediate loads (between 1000-2000 Gbps), and then start to increase again for higher loads. This “dip” presumably occurs for cases where the granularity of the transceiver rates coincides with the network load such that most flows can use P2P equipment. For example, for the 6 node network, a traffic load of 2000 Gbps assuming uniform traffic indicates that each node sends $2000/5=400$ Gbps of traffic to every other node. Since the granularity of the transceivers is 400 Gbps, these flows can use P2P transceivers, with no benefit coming from P2MP functionality. As we move above or below this “dipping point”, P2MP brings more significant savings for all traffic types, particularly with respect to spectrum and IP hops. Note that since the traffic load ρ refers to the average load per node, which is distributed among traffic flows to all the remaining nodes, this “dip” occurs at higher nodal loads for larger networks, and also for more uniform traffic. Furthermore, the same ρ value corresponds to larger total network loads in larger networks and spectral saturation is achieved for lower ρ values. This indicates that for larger networks, uniform traffic flows achieve higher savings than HS flows over more network loads than in smaller networks. On the other hand, for smaller network sizes, P2MP benefits are more pronounced for HS traffic over more load values, particularly as ρ increases.

Regarding spectrum usage, advantages of P2MP become increasingly important as the load increases, not only due to higher absolute savings, but also because P2MP can accommodate considerably higher network loads before spectral saturation where P2P solutions would cause blocking. With respect to average IP hops, P2MP technology allows for establishing nearly single-hop solutions for almost all loads and HS proportions, significantly reducing IP costs and latency with respect to P2P solutions.

The implications of this behavior in P2MP designs are fundamental and far reaching. In P2P networks, a full mesh of optical connections translates to a growth in the number of transceivers proportional to the *square* in the number of nodes, and thus becomes cost-inefficient for most loads. In contrast, P2MP technology, thanks to subcarrier aggregation, allows for establishing (close to) full mesh optical connections with fewer transceivers, and is a cost-effective solution for rings with a number of nodes in our range of interest.

Denser optical connectivities, with a full-mesh being the extreme case, enable several advantages, stemming from that fact that traffic flows traverse *less* IP hops on average (1 in full-mesh) when crossing the ring. These advantages include lower latency incurred by the OEO conversions and IP layer processing, and less IP layer equipment costs (both CAPEX and OPEX, e.g., energy consumption costs). Note that the IP layer cost savings are independent of α , as they do not depend on P2MP transceiver costs.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we investigate the potential benefits of employing Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) coherent optics based on digital subcarrier

multiplexing in ring networks. There are only a few studies available in the literature that evaluate the potential savings P2MP optics can bring, and for the most part, they concern reduction of transceiver costs in metro aggregation scenarios with Hub-and-Spoke (H&S) traffic patterns. Here, we perform a case study on fault tolerant ring networks with different traffic profiles, varying load and fraction of uniform and H&S traffic. We propose Mixed Integer Linear models for multilayer capacity planning and transceiver allocation assuming P2P and P2MP transceivers, along with a heuristic approach for the P2MP variant. We evaluate the obtained solutions, not only with respect to transceiver costs, but also IP hops and spectrum usage to assess the potential benefits of this technology. Results indicate that P2MP optics can bring savings for all traffic types. Transceiver costs savings are achieved for higher HS fractions, becoming progressively significant as loads increase. Although P2MP solutions do not bring transceiver cost savings for lower HS fractions in larger networks, these solutions can still offer other advantages such as better spectrum usage and fewer IP hops. More efficient spectrum usage is achieved for almost all traffic profiles, although the savings are most significant at high loads and for higher HS proportions. These P2MP spectrum efficiencies directly translate into significant extra capacity available in the same ring, in P2MP design. Furthermore, P2MP transceivers allow for fewer IP hops, yielding lower latency and IP layer costs, for almost all loads and all traffic profiles. The results presented in this paper can serve as an important steppingstone in evaluating the possible advantages of employing P2MP equipment in future optical networks and their application scope. Further work in the research community is needed, including evaluations in more general meshed network topologies.

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